

THE PLACE OF THE BUKHARA WATER SUPPLY MUSEUM IN THE CITY WATER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Annotation: This article highlights the fact that the Bukhara Water Supply Museum is a unique institution dedicated to the history of water management in one of the most ancient cities of Central Asia, and the place and significance of the Bukhara Water Supply Museum in the city water management system.

Keywords: Problems of the Aral Sea crisis, modern solutions for water security, ceramic pipes, wooden and metal tools, urban water distribution, progress and problems in environmental restoration.

The Bukhara Water Supply Museum plays an important role in preserving and promoting the history of water management in Bukhara, which has a rich heritage of hydraulic engineering. By displaying historical documents, photographs, maps and artifacts related to irrigation systems, the museum illuminates the evolution of water supply methods - from ancient aqueducts (underground canals) to modern infrastructure. In addition to its educational function, the museum serves as a bridge between past and present water management practices. It raises public awareness of sustainable water use, the problems of the Aral Sea crisis and the efforts being made to effectively allocate water in Bukhara. Through exhibitions and research, the museum contributes to ensuring that traditional knowledge informs modern solutions to Bukhara's water security.

The Bukhara Water Supply Museum is a unique institution dedicated to the history of water management in one of the oldest cities in Central Asia. "The Bukhara Water Supply Museum was established as part of the Bukhara State Museum-Reserve in 1991 on an area of 80.3 sq.m. in the historical monument of Chashmai Ayyub". Located within the Chashmai Ayyub complex, this compact but fascinating museum allows visitors to see the ingenious methods used by the Bukhara people to store and distribute water in an arid environment. A UNESCO World Heritage Site and a major stop on the Silk Road, Bukhara flourished despite its desert location. The city's survival depended on advanced hydraulic engineering. Clay pipes were used in medieval Bukhara's water systems. Wooden and metal tools were used to dig and store aqueducts.

Although small, the Bukhara Water Supply Museum is a gem for history and engineering enthusiasts. It tells the story of how a desert city flourished through innovation. "In June 2019, the interior and exterior of the museum underwent

major renovation. The total area is 160 sq.m., the exhibition area is 90 sq.m., and 60 exhibits from the collection are on display on the site. The exhibition consists of 2 halls and 5 main sections” .

The museum has the following halls:

The first hall focuses on traditional water sources (wells, wings, cisterns).

The second hall houses exhibitions on urban water distribution (pipes, baths, canals). The renovation after 2019 will make the museum a more attractive place for travelers interested in the innovations of the Silk Road.

The fifth section of the Bukhara Water Supply Museum provides a fascinating look at how water management has developed in the region since 1991, when Uzbekistan gained independence. The fifth section, entitled “Water Supply in Bukhara during the Years of Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, covers the work carried out in the field of irrigation in the Bukhara oasis, measures taken to solve the Aral Sea problem through photographs, maps, and a reference book. . This section covers the changes in irrigation and water supply in the Bukhara oasis since Uzbekistan gained independence. It demonstrates efforts to improve water resources management through photographs, maps, and fact sheets. It also discusses measures being taken to address the Aral Sea crisis, with an emphasis on sustainable solutions and regional water resources management. The section provides a visual and informative overview of the progress and challenges in water supply and environmental restoration in the Bukhara region.

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